

**ANALYSIS OF IMPACT OF TAX ON ECONOMIC GROWTH IN
NIGERIA: 1986 - 2021**

BY

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**A DISSERTATION SUBMITTED TO THE POSTGRADUATE SCHOOL
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DECLARATION

I declare that this dissertation entitled, “Analysis of the impact of tax on economic growth in Nigeria: 1986-2021”, has been carried out by me in the Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Abuja, under the supervision of Dr. David Okoroafor; the information derived from literature has been duly acknowledged in the text and a list of reference provided. No part of this dissertation was previously presented for another degree or diploma at this or any other institution.

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CERTIFICATION

The dissertation entitled “Analysis of Impact of Tax on Economic Growth in Nigeria: 1986-2021” by Yahaya Ismail with Reg. No: 19/409ECNH/036 meet the regulation governing the award of the degree of Master of Science (M.Sc.) Economics in Department of Economics, Faculty of Social Sciences, University of Abuja and is accepted for its contribution to knowledge and literary appreciation.

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DEDICATION

This dissertation is dedicated to Almighty Allah the creator of one and all, the author and finisher of our faiths who saw me through this programme, and to all and sundry who have made great input towards the completion of this programme.

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of tax on economic growth in Nigeria from 1986-2021, with special focus on Companies Income Tax, Value Added Tax, and Petroleum Profit Tax. Annual time series data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical bulletin and National Bureau of Statistics. The Johansen test of co-integration revealed that there were at least one co-integrating equation in the long-run and there are stable and long-term equilibrium relationships among the variables. The study used a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) to establish the nature and strength of relationship between tax and economic growth. Granger causality test found a causal relationship among GDP and the different tax components. The impulse response functions and the variance decomposition analysis through Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) upheld the findings as follows: A one standard deviation shock applied to gross domestic product produces positive effect on GDP throughout the period. Therefore, it suggested that there was an evidence in support of positive effect of GDP on its own shocks in Nigeria. A one standard deviation shock to CIT initially has positive perceptible effect on GDP in the short-run, however, for a long period it has negative perceptible effect on GDP and causes output to decrease. A one standard deviation shock to VAT has a huge and positive effect on GDP in the short run. The effect becomes noticeable in the long run. Lastly, a one standard deviation shock to PPT has positive but low effect on GDP. Between period 5 and 6.5, PPT has no effect on GDP. However, the effect becomes noticeable again as subsequent period showed that PPT's shock responded positively to GDP. It is therefore recommended that, to increase the level of Companies' Income Tax (CIT) and tax compliance in Nigeria, the government should make an effort to promote businesses by providing basic public services such as easy access loans to every nook and cranny of the nation. Government should stop all leakages in the petroleum industry so that the Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) collected from Nigerian crude oil can support and advance Nigeria's economic growth. To increase the Value Added Tax (VAT) base, Government should provide an enabling environment for businesses and innovations to thrive such tax reduction and security.

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

There is little consensus among academics regarding the role that taxes play in a nation's economic development; some claim that taxes have positive effects (Eze & Onyedikachi, 2020; Ibadin & Oluwatuyi, 2021), others claim that taxes have negative effects (Aliyu & Mustapha, 2020). The literature on economic growth up until the early 1990s was primarily concerned with modelling an economy with a long-run equilibrium where output is exogenously determined by technological advancement, assumed to be determined outside the system, and where the instruments of government policy have no long-term impact on the growth rate. The fundamental tenet of the argument, according to Solow (1956), is that where the rule of diminishing returns to scale is in effect, the Neo-classical economist views attributes economic growth to increases in physical and human capital (Chiumia & Simwaka, 2012).

Romer (1986) has opposing viewpoints, which are represented in their theories of endogenous growth. They suggested that government policies, can have an impact on economic growth. This suggests that immediate government action might stimulate economic growth. Taxation, however, is a cost incurred by the government while formulating various frameworks and policies for economic progress. Five potential processes are listed by Tosun & Abizabeh (2005) for how taxes as a tool of fiscal policy impact economic growth. First, taxes like corporate

and personal income taxes and capital gains taxes can lower investment rates. (Magaji, Musa, Eke & Yakeen, 2022) argument is in agreement with this. Second, taxes have the potential to stifle the expansion of the labour force by favouring leisure over work. Third, by discouraging investment in Research Development (R&D), tax policy can harm productivity growth. Fourthly, according to the Harbinger Framework, taxes may cause resources to move to industries with lower productivity. Finally, because large tax burdens will demotivate societal productivity, high taxes on the labour supply can distort the effective utilization of human resources. Endogenous growth models have been used in several recent theoretical studies to enhance the effects of a fundamental tax change on economic growth. Gale & Samwick (2014) investigate how taxes affect the potential Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and the growth of the supply side of the economy. A rise in the yearly growth rate, a one-time boost in the size of the economy that doesn't affect future growth rates but puts the economy on a higher growth path, or a combination of both could be the result of the expansion. They concentrate on the supply side of the economy, which contrasts with the short-term phenomena known as "economic growth," wherein an increase in aggregate demand, in a sluggish economy, can improve GDP and help bring actual GDP into line with potential GDP Engen & Skinner (1996).

Taxation has become a topic of discussion and debate in Nigeria due to the need to find a long-term alternative to oil revenue (Adeyemi & Adedapo, 2021). Tax revenue and non-tax revenue are the only two sources of income for the government

(Oladipupo & Oladipo, 2022). Tax revenue mobilization in Nigeria must be accelerated. Both academic and socio-political circles have vigorously disputed the impact of taxes on economic growth and development (Etim, Nweze, Umoffon & Asogwa, 2020; Magaji, S., Musa, I., Yakeen, A.O.Y. & Eke, C.I., 2022). At one extreme are those who support tax cuts and claim that doing so will increase economic growth by citing the benefits that lower taxes have on incentives to work, save, and invest. (Ergete & Dahlby, 2012).

In Nigeria, tax revenue has historically represented a minor part of overall revenue generation compared to the Federal Government's primary source of income (Otu & Adejumo, 2013). According to records, the current downturn in oil prices has reduced the amount of money that Nigeria's Federal, State, and Local Governments have available for distribution (Afuberon & Okoye, 2014). Therefore, Nigeria's excessive reliance on oil as a significant source of income has seriously hampered the country's ability to experience sustainable economic growth. The fluctuation in oil prices on the global market has caused Nigerians and the government to seriously consider the necessity to diversify the economy. It is noteworthy that there is a paradigm shift toward tax income as a better alternative form of revenue creation globally, and the Nigerian government now has a pressing need to produce sufficient tax revenue (Afuberon & Okoye, 2014).

How to ensure taxpayers' voluntary compliance is one of the many issues that tax administration in the Nigerian economy faces. No one wants to pay taxes, thus taxpayers do not much like the tax collector, whom they see as the government's

toll collector. The poor performance of the majority of state governments in terms of providing amenities for the tax-paying population through government expenditure and otherwise (Aluko, Musa & Ismail, 2024) exacerbates the taxman's difficulty. Voluntary compliance issues resulted from mutual mistrust and a lack of confidence in the government, as represented in this case by the taxman. Nigerian tax rules are complicated and challenging for the average taxpayer to understand, and in some circumstances, even literate officials face challenges (Magaji & Ayo, 2016). Along with a lack of comprehension, many taxpayers are not even aware that certain taxes are even charged. This, coupled with the lack of information, the tax official's sloth, the unwillingness of the taxpayers, and the propensity for "quick fixes," supports the employment of the best judgment approach. This could be a result of inadequate tax education and a lacklustre effort on the part of tax authorities to perform their duties related to public awareness. If customers had the option, they wouldn't want to purchase tax because it is an imposition, according to Ocheoha (2000). He reports that taxes are levied by the government primarily to generate the necessary funds to pay for general administration and defence expenses. He argues that paying people emoluments, salaries, and wages for leaders or those in authority, their aides, as well as the salaries of city officials, police, and military personnel, constitutes the cost of general administration. Since taxes now serve a larger range of purposes, the government uses them as a true administrative tool. It is impossible to overstate the importance of taxation as a subject that merits study. Abudulrazaq (2002), many different aspects of Nigerian taxation should be

researched and applied. He suggested that technical proficiency with a strong collection of primary sources is required and that the proficiency might be tested in a variety of methods, from simple computation to transaction planning. People in positions of authority levy taxes and fees for several reasons. According to Musgrave (2004), taxes and fees are taken out of the private sector without leaving the government liable to the payee.

The total amount of taxes collected by the nation in 2019 was 5.26 trillion naira (\$13.5 billion), according to the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS). However, the estimated 19 million tax-paying individuals show that around 50.5 million employed Nigerians do not pay taxes FIRS (2021). The government uses tax revenue to carry out its duties, including providing public goods, maintaining law and order, defending against internal and external aggression, regulating trade and business to ensure social and economic upkeep, and using fiscal tools to promote economic stability. The taxes are levied on individuals, groups, corporate entities and other institutions chargeable to tax, and play a vital role in the economic planning and development of nations.

However, although charges and borrowing entail voluntary transactions, tax is a mandatory imposition. In other words, one of the key characteristics that set tax apart from other fees is that it is not a quid pro quo expenditure, which implies that a taxpayer shouldn't demand or anticipate receiving a similar exchange of products or services in return for the tax they have paid. Increased tax evasion, avoidance, and ineffective and inefficient personal income tax administration in the Nigerian

economy were caused by a high-level incidence of corruption in the administration of personal income taxation. Corruption and other vices in the administration of personal income tax in the Nigerian economy are to blame for the system's obvious inefficiency, which is demonstrated by the rise in tax defaulters, evasion, and avoidance. Therefore, additional research in Nigeria is warranted in light of the contradictory findings of earlier studies evaluating the impact of tax income on economic growth. In light of the foregoing, this study makes an effort to examine the empirical analysis of the impact of tax on Nigerian economic growth from 1986-2021.

1.9 Statement of the Problem

According to Musgrave (2004), taxes and fees are taken out of the private sector without leaving the government liable to the payee. However, although charges and borrowing entail voluntary transactions, tax is a mandatory imposition. In other words, one of the key characteristics that set tax apart from other fees is that it is not a quid pro quo expenditure, which implies that a taxpayer shouldn't demand or anticipate receiving a similar exchange of products or services in return for the tax they have paid. Increased tax evasion, avoidance, and ineffective and inefficient personal income tax administration in the Nigerian economy were caused by a high-level incidence of corruption in the administration of personal income taxation. Corruption and other vices in the administration of personal income tax in the Nigerian economy are to blame for the system's obvious inefficiency, which is demonstrated by the rise in tax defaulters, evasion, and avoidance. Therefore,

additional research in Nigeria is warranted in light of the contradictory findings of earlier studies evaluating the impact of tax income on economic growth. In light of the foregoing, this study will make an effort to provide answers to the following questions, which serve as the fundamental components of the issues it raises.

1.10 Research Questions

The following research questions were addressed under the problem definition above:

1.10.1 Does the Companies Income Tax (CIT) have an impact on economic growth in Nigeria?

1.10.2 What is the relationship between Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) and economic growth in Nigeria?

1.10.3 Is the Value Added Tax (VAT) having a significant impact on economic growth in Nigeria?

1.11 The Objective of the Study

The general objective of the study was to examine the impact of tax on economic growth in Nigeria. While the specific objectives are to:

- i. examine the relationship between Companies' Income Tax (CIT) and Nigerian economic growth.
- ii. study the impact of Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) on Nigerian economic growth.
- iii. ascertain the effectiveness of Value Added Tax (VAT) on Nigerian economic growth.

1.12 Statement of Hypotheses

In line with the above objectives, the following null hypotheses were formulated for this study:

H₀₁: there is no significant relationship between Companies' Income Tax (CIT) and economic growth in Nigeria.

H₀₂: there is no significant relationship between Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) and economic growth in Nigeria.

H₀₃: there is no significant relationship between Value Added Tax (VAT) and economic growth in Nigeria.

1.13 Significance of the Study

There are avalanche of literature on tax revenue and Nigeria's economic growth, including works by Abomaye-Nimenibo, Friday, and Hope Chika, (2018); Oluwasegun and Joseph (2020), Oluwole (2022), as well as Etim, Nweze, Umoffon, and Asogwa (2020). This study is significantly different because it took into account the post-SAP era, when the liberalization policy started to take full effect and encouraged more Foreign Direct Investment into the Nigerian economy, to examine the impact of companies income tax (CIT), petroleum profit tax (PPT), and value-added tax (VAT) on the gross domestic product (GDP). This study will help decision-makers select the best tax personal income policy and penalties for tax

violation or evasion by people, organizations, or businesses. Theoretically, it will assist in educating management, administrators, and tax officers on the importance of ongoing tax assessment to broaden the government's source of revenue. Additionally, it will help in educating the general public and taxpayers on the importance of upholding their national citizenship obligations. The study is crucial for informing readers, particularly those involved in financial administration, about how personal income taxation is administered. Finally, it will act as a resource for academics and students who want to perform fieldwork in the future.

1.14 Scope of the Study

This study covers a period from 1986 to 2021 and analyzed how to tax income affects economic growth in Nigeria. This scope's justification is to be able to take into account the post-SAP era when liberalization policies started to take its full effects and encouraged more FDI into the Nigerian economy. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Companies' Income Tax (CIT), Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT), and Value Added Tax (VAT) were the four variables used. The Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria and National Bureau of Statistics was the source of the annual data.

1.15 Structure of the Study

There are five main chapters, including references and appendices, make up for this Dissertation. Sections and Subsections are included in each chapter, with the introduction serving as the opening chapter, which include; Background information, a description of the research problem, research questions, the purpose

of the study, a statement of the research hypotheses, the significance of the study, and the scope of the study. The second chapter includes a review of the literature on the subject, which is further divided into sections on conceptual analysis, theoretical analysis, empirical analysis, and theoretical framework. Chapter three contains the Research Methodology. Chapter four contains a data presentation and discussion of results, while chapter five has the summary, policy recommendations and conclusion.

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW AND THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Conceptual Review

The principles employed in this study are explicitly discussed below;

2.1.1 Concept of taxation

Onakoya, Afintinni, and Ogundajo (2017), the word "tax" is derived from the Latin word "taxo," which means to estimate the value or compute the value. A recurring and required payment made by citizens to the government for it to deliver services that they use is known as a tax. As old as the "State" itself are these kinds of payments made to the government. The primary source of public funding for ages has been the public domain. Azubike (2009), a tax is a mandatory charge that the government imposes on a person or their property to fund social services and foster societal economic growth. Similarly, Chigbu and Njoku (2015) underline that taxes are a significant source of income for any country and that they are frequently utilized as a tool to close the wealth gap.

Afubero and Okoye (2014) view taxation as a mandatory levy imposed by the government through its agencies on the capital, income, and consumption of its subjects. Thus, taxes are levied on individual income, including wages, business profits, interests, dividends, discounts, and royalties, in addition to business earnings, petroleum profits, and capital gains. An additional definition of tax is a compulsory charge imposed by tax authorities on wealth, money, or individuals for which the taxpayers do not specifically or directly receive anything in return (Shang,

2016). Tax revenue is acknowledged as the most significant financial source for governmental public spending among the many ways that governments might earn income (Frecknall-Hughes, 2014).

2.1.2 Concept of tax in Nigeria

Appah (2010), the Taxes and Levies (approved list for Collection) Decree, 1998 clearly defines the jurisdictions of each of the three levels of government in Nigeria, the Federal, State, and Local Government areas. Concern over the Nigerian tax system's low productivity has been voiced by several governments. This has primarily been attributed to flaws in the tax administration and collecting system, complicated legislation, and apathy, particularly on the part of individuals outside the tax net. This is because, in the 1980s, several developing nations implemented tax reforms as a way to meet spending requirements. The majority of these reforms, however, prioritized tax structure over tax administration to increase revenue from current tax sources.

In the words of Unegbu and Irefin (2011), the Nigerian tax system has undergone several modifications intended to improve tax administration at a low cost of enforcement. The introduction of the Taxpayer Identification Number (TIN), which went into effect in February 2008, the Automated Tax System (ATS) that facilitates tracking of tax positions, the E-payment System (EPS) that improves the smoothness of the payment process and lowers the incidence of tax touts, and the enforcement scheme that employs special tax officers in collaboration with other security agencies to ensure strict tax compliance are some of the most recent reforms. The

integrated tax offices and authorities now have the autonomy to assess, collect, and record tax as a result of an improvement in the country's tax administration brought about by Section 8(a) of the Federal Inland Revenue Service Establishment Act of 2007. Despite this progress, several controversial issues still need urgent attention, including the need for an appropriate tax authority to administer taxes, the problem of multiple taxes administered by various levels of government that occasionally impose welfare costs, and the lack of a database that encourages tax evasion in the nation. Unegbu and Irefin (2011) noted that the country's long-standing corruption problem undermines the taxpayers' faith and trust in the government's ability to carry out its civic duty. Most facilities are frequently privately sourced and the infrastructure deficit is a critical concern; people frequently question the purpose of tax collection and thus develop a propensity to cheat on taxes (El-Yaqub et al., 2024).

2.1.2.1 Company Income Tax (CIT) in Nigeria

Appah (2010) submits that all Nigerian corporations that have their profits accumulated, derived from, brought into, or received in Nigeria are subject to Company Income Tax. Both private and public limited liability firms are required to pay taxes on the profits of non-resident businesses operating in Nigeria. The Income Tax Management Act of 1961 served as the foundation for CIT, which was established by the Companies Income Tax Act (CITA) of 1979. It is one of the taxes that the Federal Inland Income Service (FIRS) administers and collects, and it makes a sizable contribution to the government's income profile. Such profits shall be deemed to accrue in Nigeria wherever they have arisen (worldwide) and whether or

not they have been brought into or received in Nigeria (Ugochukwu and Azubike, 2015). Profits from any kind of trade or business are among them, as is rent from the use of property, dividends, interest, royalties, discounts, charges, annuities, fees for rendered services, and other annual gains or profits. Therefore, both Nigerian and foreign enterprises must pay Company Income Tax Act in Nigeria. One of the most significant sources of income for the government of Nigeria is the company income tax.

2.1.2.2 Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT)

Fasoranti (2013), PPT entails taxation of income derived from petroleum operations. He pointed out that many rules governing the taxes of profits from petroleum operations had been passed as a result of the importance of petroleum to Nigeria's economy. Oil sector upstream operations are subject to the petroleum profit tax, which is related to rent, royalties, oil mining prospecting, and exploratory leases. In Nigeria, it is a significant tax in terms of overall income because it generates over 70% of government revenue and 95% of foreign exchange earnings. Nwokoh and Kiabel, (2009). Ilaboya (2012), the accounting period's real profit serves as the base period for the Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT). This suggests that the basis period for any evaluation year is the same as the company's accounting period.

2.1.2.3 Value Added Tax (VAT)

Value-Added Tax has been defined in a variety of ways by various authors and writers. Value-Added Tax is characterized as a consumption tax where the tax burden is borne by the consumer, according to Abata (2014). He explained that the

burden of paying taxes is ultimately transferred from the manufacturer to the wholesaler, retailer, and then consumer. Therefore, it follows that the only way to avoid paying VAT is to stop consuming any goods or services that are subject to it. A person who trades in vatable goods and services for money is referred to as being vatable. Indirect taxes, Olurotimi (2013), are levied on every sale, starting with the cycle of production and distribution and ending with consumer sales. He even went so far as to suggest that consumers pay VAT as part of the price of goods, effectively making VAT a consumption tax that is collected throughout the entire production process. With few exceptions, VAT is a generally based consumption tax that is imposed on products and services at a different rate depending on the jurisdiction. The burden of Value Added Tax is ultimately borne by the final consumer and is collected at each stage of the production and distribution chain, Okoye and Gbegi (2013). It is a multi-stage tax imposed on the value added to goods and services as they proceed through various stages of the production and distribution process and to services as they are rendered.

2.1.3 Concept of Economic Growth

Because it has long been acknowledged as a crucial goal of economic policy, a sizable body of research has been devoted to explaining how economic growth might be accomplished (Fadare, 2010). Economic growth is the expansion of a nation's potential GDP or output. If the societal rate of return on investment is higher than the private return, for instance, tax measures may encourage growth rates and utility levels. According to Olopade & Olopade (2010), the ideal tax policy

concentrates on the characteristics of services in development models that include public services. The causes of states' different rates of growth over time have also been clarified by economic growth, and this affects the government's monetary policy as well as the tax and expenditure levels that determine growth rates. Economic growth is the gradual increase in the market value of the goods that a country's economy produces (Magaji, S., Ayo, A. A., Ibrahim Musa & Ali, S. (2019). Relative impact of monetary policy instructions on economic growth in Nigeria. *Lapai Journal of Economics*. 3(2), 93-118. 2016 Economic Outlook for Africa Typically, it is expressed as the real gross domestic product, or real GDP, growth rate in percentage terms. The per capita income growth rate, commonly referred to as the GDP per capita growth rate, is more important. An increase in per capita income is referred to as intensive growth. According to Gordon (1999), extensive growth is defined as GDP growth that is exclusively attributed to gains in territory or population.

2.2 Theoretical Review

To help the government choose how to accomplish justice or equity in taxation, economists have proposed a variety of taxation theories or guiding principles across time. In a nutshell, the basic theories or principles are:

2.2.1 Benefit Theory

The benefit theory approach was initially developed by two Swedish economists from the Stockholm School, Johan Gustaf Knut Wicksell. (1896). and Lindahl, Erik. (1919). The theory contends that the state ought to tax people in proportion to the

benefits they obtain from the government. A person should pay taxes to the government based on the benefits they receive from government actions. This theory has been subjected to many criticisms based on the following reasons:

In the first place, if the state upholds a specific link between the advantages bestowed and the benefits derived. It will go against the tax's fundamental tenet. As is common knowledge, taxes are mandatory payments made to the government to cover costs and provide for the general welfare. A tax does not directly result in anything. Secondly, it is impossible to quantify the benefit received annually by a specific person because the majority of government expenditures are made for the benefit of all of its residents. Thirdly, because they use the state's services more frequently, the poor will be required to pay the highest taxes if this theory is put into practice. It is against the justice concept if we raise taxes on the poor.

2.2.2 The Cost of Service Theory

The 'Cost of Service' theory of taxes, which contends that taxpayers should be taxed under the cost of the services that the government delivers, is the opposite of the benefit theory. According to the cost-benefit postulation, the tax that each person should pay must be proportional to the cost of the benefits they receive. Some economists believed that the concept of equity or justice in taxation would be satisfied if the state collected the actual cost of the service provided by the people. The cost of service principle can undoubtedly be used to some extent in situations where the services are provided for a fee and are very simple to calculate (postal services, railroad services, and energy supplies). However, because it cannot be

precisely defined, the majority of the expenses expended by the state cannot be fixed for each person. How, for instance, can the cost of service to various individuals of the police, military, and judicial systems be quantified? Dalton (2006) has also disproved this argument, arguing that there is no tax quid pro quo.

2.2.3. Ability to Pay Theory

Pigou (1920) first proposed this theory, which contends that each person should pay taxes based on his or her financial capacity to cover the cost of governmental expenses. The principle of equity or justice in taxation is the same as the ability to pay theory of taxation. There should be "no quid pro quo" since those with greater earnings should pay more taxes than those with lower incomes. Taxes should be collected based on a person's ability to pay, as this seems more fair and logical. The definition of someone's ability to pay is the theory's main flaw. The most well-known and widely accepted tenet of fairness or justice in taxation is that a nation's residents should contribute to the government following their financial capacity. Taxes should be assessed based on a person's ability to pay them, which seems quite fair and logical. For instance, if Mr A has a higher taxable capacity than Mr B, the former should be required to pay more taxes than the latter. Therefore, this approach gives the payer's capability priority when estimating tax revenue. Accordingly, it is assumed that those with greater incomes will pay more than those with lower incomes (Jacob, Josiah, and Solomon, 2021). In light of this theory, everyone should only be subject to taxes that they can afford. The government can maximize the distributive impact of taxation in this way.

2.3 Empirical Review

Tax income, economic growth, and the human development index are all examined by Ibadin and Oluwatuyi (2021). The study examines the effects of many significant taxes on the real gross domestic product (RGDP) and human development index (HDI), including company income tax (CIT), petroleum profit tax (PPT), value-added tax (VAT), and customs and excise duty (CED). RGDP and HDI have been widely employed as indicators of economic progress and growth, respectively. Annual time series data for the years 1994 to 2017 were used in the study. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test, the Johansen multivariate cointegration approach, and the Error Correction Model (ECM) method, which is mostly used for time series analysis, were all applied in the study's methodology. The results indicated a favourable and significant correlation between tax revenue and HDI. The outcome shows that, as the dependent variable, RGDP has a greater impact on HDI than tax revenue does. Because HDI is more comprehensive than RGDP, which, according to their findings, presents a weaker picture of linkages between tax income and economic growth in Nigeria, they advise placing more trust in it as a result. Based on this, and given that HDI criteria are known for their measurability, both in quantitative and qualitative terms, and proposes tax policies that are development-driven.

The relationship between tax revenue components and economic growth in Nigeria from 1989 to 2018 is examined by Etim, Nweze, Umoffon, and Asogwa (2020). The increased global emphasis on increasing tax collections relative to Gross Domestic

Product (GDP) and diversifying national economies' revenue sources served as the study's driving force. Data on the GDP and tax receipts were taken from the Federal Inland Revenue Service's (FIRS) annual reports and the Central Bank of Nigeria's (CBN) statistical bulletin. Data were analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics, including the Granger Causality tests, the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM), the Augmented-Dickey Fuller (ADF) stationary unit root test, and correlational statistics. The ECM was used to correct for differences between the long-run and short-run effects of explanatory factors. The ECM coefficient showed that the explanatory variables adjusted between the short-run and long-run effects extremely slowly. Economic growth (GDP) and personal income taxes (PIT; 3.7045), petroleum profit taxes (PPT; 2.76295), and corporate income taxes (CIT; 3.64429) have a positive and statistically significant relationship, whereas EDT and CED have no such relationship at the 0.05 level of significance. Economic growth and EDT, CED, and PPT are all positively correlated with one another, according to the Causality Test results. The findings demonstrate that tax revenue components are crucial to Nigeria's economic growth and advise that government policies on taxation matters be managed delicately to stimulate interventionist actions that will accelerate economic growth.

Using annual secondary time series data from 1981 to 2020, Oluwasegun and Joseph (2020), explore the dynamic relationship between tax income, infrastructure improvement, and economic growth in Nigeria. The Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) and Phillip Perron (PP) tests were used to investigate the series' unit root

properties, and the Johansen Co integration test was used to determine whether or not the series are cointegrated. The outcomes show that all of the series are nonintegrated and of order 1 integration. A vector autoregression (VAR) causality test and a VAR at-first difference model were conducted to investigate the direction of causality and the correlation among the variables. The findings show a unidirectional correlation between tax revenue and infrastructure development, as well as a bidirectional causality between infrastructure development and economic growth. Based on the results of the impulse response tests, it can be concluded that while infrastructure has a considerable impact on tax revenue received, infrastructure has no discernible impact on economic growth. The study suggests that government should more fully embrace fiscal responsibility by holding taxpayers more accountable for the provision of higher-quality infrastructures that can foster economic growth.

From 1981 to 2017, Aliyu and Mustapha (2020) examines the effect of tax income on economic growth in Nigeria. It makes use of time series data from the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) webpage, FIRS yearly publications, and CBN statistical bulletins. The dynamics and long-term effects of independent variables on the dependent variable were estimated using the OLS and ARDL approaches. The variables are co-integrated, as shown by the ARDL bound test, and the ARDL long-run estimation showed that the GDP is significantly and positively correlated with petroleum profit, value-added tax, and government domestic debt. Additionally, corporation income tax and excise and customs taxes were large but had a

detrimental effect on economic growth. As a result of the low contribution of tax revenue to GDP identified during the study's duration, they advise the government to step up efforts to increase tax collection. This can be accomplished by closing all tax law loopholes and bringing in additional potential taxpayers, particularly from the unorganized sector.

In Nigeria between the 1999 and 2018, Ukeme and Olayinka (2020) examines the impact of tax revenue on public debt and capital spending. The Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) was used as a source of secondary data. To investigate the impact of the independent variables (represented by value-added tax, company income tax, petroleum profit tax, customs and excise duty) on the dependent variable (external debt, internal debt, and capital expenditure), it used the ordinary least square regression method by the E-views program. Descriptive Statistics, Unit Roots using Augmented Dickey-Fuller, Cointegration tests using the Bounds Test, and Vector Error Correction Model are the data treatments utilized for the times series secondary data. The results show that tax income had a statistically significant positive and negative impact on capital expenditure and state debt. The impact of tax collection on Nigeria's external debt and capital spending was mixed. Oluwole (2022) investigates whether tax income (Company Income Tax, Custom Excise Duty, and Value-Added Tax) will have an impact on Nigeria's economic development either alone or collectively. This study uses an ex-post facto research design as a result. The study's findings ranged over 40 years from 1980 to 2020. The National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS), and

Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) were the sources of the study's data. The acquired data were examined using the ARDL (autoregressive distributive lag model). The results of this study showed a long-term association between tax collections and Nigeria's economic growth. The implication is that long-term economic growth and real gross domestic product in Nigeria will be considerably impacted by successful tax revenue mobilization in the economy. Additionally, it was shown that over time, customs and excise duties had a negative and considerable impact on Nigeria's economic growth. In Nigeria, it was discovered that over time, Company Income Tax (CIT) had a marginally beneficial impact on real GDP. Additionally, it was discovered that value-added tax in Nigeria had a long-term, beneficial, and large impact on the real gross domestic product. This study finds that tax income, as measured by CIT, CED, and VAT, significantly contributes to Nigeria's economic growth. It advises that the government strengthen the tax system because it has an impact on both economic growth and development.

The relationship between taxation and Nigeria's economic growth is investigated by Dibia and Onwuchekwa (2019). Utilizing time series data for the years 1981 to 2016, it explicitly examined the relationships between firm income tax, petroleum profit tax, and the economic growth of Nigeria as measured by Real Gross Domestic Product. A research design known as *ex post facto* was used. The results reveal that the Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) in Nigeria is positively and significantly impacted by the Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) and the Company Income Tax (CIT). The study recommended that the Nigerian government implement fiscal policies to

promote investments in the real estate sector and generate employment opportunities; work toward bringing social amenities to every corner of the nation as this will increase tax compliance in Nigeria; and foster an environment that will encourage entrepreneurship and innovation to increase income derived from tax proceeds.

Olatunji (2019) researched the efficiency of VAT administration in Nigeria to increase government revenue and foster economic growth. To analyze the data, he employed chi-square and basic percentages. The research revealed a strong relationship between VAT and GDP.

Abomaye-Nimenibo et al. (2018) looked at how taxes affect the economy. With GDP as the dependent variable and Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT), Company Income Tax (CIT), and Customs and Excise Duties (CED) as the independent variables, the study was prepared to empirically examine the relationship between tax revenue and economic growth in Nigeria from 1980 to 2015. The Multiple Regression Analysis approach was used to conduct the study's analysis. The primary analytical method used with Econometric software (EViews 9.0) was the Ordinary Least Square (OLS) method of econometrics. Their findings indicate that there is no substantial correlation between the taxation of petroleum profits, corporate income taxes, and customs and excise fees and Nigeria's economic expansion. However, if integrated properly and methodically, taxes have the potential to have a positive impact on the economy.

The empirical evidence varies across economics, data, and methodology; some findings indicate a negative impact while others demonstrate that tax revenue has

little to no impact on economic growth. Furthermore, studies have tended to use aggregated data of tax revenue or total government revenue rather than the disaggregated tax revenue components that this study seeks to examine, making the pattern of flow and the intervening relationship between tax revenue and economic growth still an open question, particularly for developing and emerging markets like Nigeria.

2.4 Gap in Literature

There is an avalanche of research on tax collection in Nigeria and its impact on economic growth and development (Abomaye-Nimenibo, Friday, and Hope Chika, 2018; Dibia and Onwuchekwa, 2019; Olatunji, 2019; Etim, Nweze, Umoffon and Asogwa, 2020; Oluwasegun and Joseph, 2020; Aliyu and Mustapha, 2020; Ukeme and Olayinka, 2020). These studies Mostly examined tax collection in Nigeria and its impact on economic growth and development and some studies also look at impact of taxation on economic growth and human development index. Furthermore, the majority of these studies have a scope gap because they typically take 19 to 30 years to collect the data. As a result, this study empirically analyzed the impact of tax on economic growth in Nigeria from 1986-2021. Economic growth was used only in this analysis instead of the previous literatures that used economic growth and development interchangeably in their analysis. This study finds more relevance and rationale in light of the gap. To fill the gap, this study subjected economic growth in the Nigerian economy and also use percentage changes in GDP to capture the impact of tax on economic growth in Nigeria.

$$Y_t = A_t K_t^\alpha L_t^\beta \dots\dots\dots (2.3)$$

where α and β are shares of capital and labour, respectively. The Cobb-Douglas production function, according to Solow (1956), is practical since it displays continuous returns to scale. Here, it's important to keep in mind that A_t is not constant but changes over time. This presumption is required to allow influences on TFP from things like foreign direct investment, research and development spending, and tax income, among others. The assumption that the functional form of Eq. (2.2) is Cobb-Douglas is widely used in the literature (see, for instance, Fosu 1990; Fosu and Aryeetey, 2008; Fosu and Magnus, 2006; Mansouri, 2005; Ram & Ramsey, 1989).

CHAPTER THREE

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

This study examined the impact of Tax on economic growth in Nigeria. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Companies' Income Tax (CIT), Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT), and Value Added Tax (VAT) are the secondary data used. These time series data were obtained from the Statistical Bulletin of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). To ascertain the genuine nature of the stationary qualities of all the variables under investigation, the present study first used the unit root test based on this concern. Since unit root issues are a regular occurrence in the majority of time series research, doing this is essential to avoid the issue of spurious regression. To determine whether all the variables are integrated in the same order, such as at the first difference $I(1)$, the Johansen Cointegration test was used. Following the cointegration test, the study's estimating technique was the Vector Error Correction (VEC) model, depending on whether the variables were cointegrated or not. Additionally, it's crucial to remember that $I(2)$ if any of the variables are integrated at order two. There would have been the usage of the Toda Yamamoto.

3.2 Model Specification and Justification

Our goal is to investigate the empirical analysis of the performance of tax in the Nigerian economy. The study adapted a model from Abomaye- Nimenibo, Friday, and Chika (2018) to achieve this. In its functional form, their original model is

specified as:

$$GDP_t = f(PPT_t, CIT_t, CED_t) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

From the above function, we derived the statistical model as follows:

$$GDP_t = \alpha + \beta_1 PPT_t + \beta_2 CIT_t + \beta_3 CED_t + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots(3.2)$$

By transforming the linear function into their log form, we have;

$$GDP = \alpha + \beta_1 LPPT + \beta_2 LCIT + \beta_3 LCED + \varepsilon \dots\dots\dots (3.3)$$

Where; GDP: Gross Domestic Product

PPT: Petroleum Profit Tax

CIT: Company Income Tax

CED: Customs and Excise Duties

α : is a constant

Our fundamental long-run model for identifying the effects of tax performance on the Nigerian economy is Equation 1. The need to incorporate a model that accommodates the short-run dynamic adjustment process, which is the speed of adjustment from short-run disequilibrium to long-run equilibrium, has been amply supported in recent econometrics literature. However, the value-added tax is missing in equation (1), hence, our new model will be:

$$GDP = f(CIT, PPT, VAT) \dots\dots\dots (3.4)$$

Where; GDP = Gross Domestic Product

CIT = Company Income Tax

PPT = Petroleum Profit Tax

VAT = Value Added Tax

Specifying the model in explicit form, we have;

$$GDP_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 CIT_t + \alpha_2 PPT_t + \alpha_3 VAT_t + U_t \dots\dots\dots (3.5)$$

GDP is the Dependent while CIT, PPT AND VAT are the independent variables.

Equation (3.5) is meant to explain the impact of tax on economic growth in Nigeria.

$\alpha_0, \alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3$, are the parameters to be estimated in the equation.

3.3 Variable Measurement and Description

In time series studies, especially those that examine interactions among real economic factors, high-frequency data is typically more suitable. This study used annual data to accurately capture the effect of tax on economic growth in Nigeria. There are available data for all variables sets for this study. The model's variables are divided into dependent and independent variables. Gross Domestic Product (GDP), which represents the entire monetary worth of all finished products and services produced inside a nation's borders in a given fiscal year, is the dependent variable. The export sector, the exchange rate, and trade or economic openness are anticipated to have a beneficial impact on GDP. Considering that the independent variables are Company Income Tax (CIT) is a tax that is paid by companies with Nigerian incorporation, whether they are residents or not. Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT): Any resident business or individual in charge of a non-resident business that explores petroleum or produces it in Nigeria is subject to the Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) and Value Added Tax (VAT), Value-Added Tax is characterized as a consumption tax where the tax burden is borne by the consumer.

3.4 Estimation and Evaluation Techniques

3.4.1 Unit Root Test To Determine Order of Integration

It is natural to estimate an Augmented Dickey-Fuller regression when examining the stationary qualities of each observed time series (Yt) over a specified period (T).

First, take into account a variable with a non-stationary time series that is produced by a first-order autoregressive process (AR(1)). Resulting in an Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test that looks like this:

The subsequent regression estimates the general form of the ADF test:

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_1 + \delta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (3.6)$$

$$\Delta Y_t = \beta_1 + \beta_2 t + \delta Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \dots \dots \dots (3.7)$$

Where Y is the time series variable under study, t is a linear time trend, Δ is the first difference operator, β₁ is the constant, n is the optimum number of lags in the dependent variable, Σ is the summation sign, and ε_t is a pure white noise error term.

Thus, Models (3.6) and (3.7) are a general form of ADF tests with trend and intercept respectively, which establishes whether the series is stationary under the null hypothesis, H₀: = 0 (meaning non-stationary), as opposed to the alternative hypothesis, H₁: 0 (indicating the series is stationary); and n denotes the ideal number of lag lengths in the dependent variable (Yt), which is solely determined by the parameter, Keep in mind that Yt refers to a certain time series variable.

The Philips-Perron (1988) unit root test was utilized as a supplemental test as this

study uses a finite number of observations, despite the argument that the ADF unit root testing approach alone is insufficient in finite samples. As previously noted, a cointegration test utilizing Johansen Multivariate cointegration would be applied if all the variables of concern were discovered to be stationary (of the same order) after taking the first or second difference but non-stationary at the level.

3.4.2 Co-integration Test

The theory behind testing for co-integration is that even while the differences between two or more time series variables are stationary in the long run, the variables themselves are trending over time (non-stationary). Because the difference between them remains stationary in this situation, these variables can be thought of as establishing a long-run equilibrium relationship (Hall, 1989). However, if the time series variables do not show a long-term equilibrium relationship, they will in theory drift apart randomly and aimlessly since their differences are not stable (Dickey and Fuller, 1981). We test for r (the greatest number of co-integrating relationships) using the trace test and the maximum Eigen-value approach.

The trace statistic is given as:

$$\lambda \text{ trace} = \sum_{n-t+1}^k \ln(I - \lambda_j)^{-T} \dots\dots\dots (3.8)$$

Where T is the number of period observations and λ_j is the i th largest Eigenvalue. The null hypothesis is that the co-integrating rank is r and the VAR process. It is pertinent to mention that before performing the Johansen co-integration test, this study used the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC) and Hannan-Quinn Information Criterion (HQIC) to determine the optimum lag length. The number of co-integrating

vectors is denoted by the r_0 ; the trace test is calculated under the null hypothesis:

$$H_0: r_0 \leq r$$

$$H_1: r_0 = r$$

Decision Rule: reject the null hypothesis if $|\tau_{\text{cal}}| > |\tau_{\text{tab}}|$ at 5% level of significance, do not reject if otherwise.

3.4.3 Causality Test

Finding the lead/lag relationship between variables is our major goal while analyzing Granger-Causality relationships. To answer the question of whether X causes Y, Granger (1969) suggests first determining how much of the current Y can be described by past values of Y and then examining whether the explanation can be strengthened by including lagged values of X. If X aids in the prediction of Y or if the coefficients on the lagged Xs are statistically significant, X is considered to be the Granger cause of Y. The frequent occurrence of two-way causation—where X Granger causes Y and Y Granger causes X—should be noted. As a result, this study examined an example of Granger causality that involves five endogenous variables: companies' income tax, petroleum profit tax, value-added tax, and gross domestic product (GDP). The phrase "X Granger-causes Y" should not be interpreted to mean that Y is X's impact or outcome. Granger-causality measures information content and precedence, although it does not automatically imply causality in the sense that the word is most commonly used. Given the difficulty of interpreting the Granger technique couched in VAR models, it is preferable to utilize greater lags in the test

regressions than fewer lags. It is essential to select a lag duration that is consistent with reasonable expectations for the longest period during which one variable could contribute to the prediction of another.

The following equations are used to determine the causality:

$$\Delta Y_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^m \gamma_i \Delta X_{t-i} + \mu \dots \dots \dots (3.9)$$

$$\Delta X_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^m \beta_i \Delta X_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^m \psi_i \Delta X_{t-i} + \mu \dots \dots \dots (3.10)$$

Where Y_t and X_t are defined as Y and X observed over periods; Δ is the difference operator; m represents the numbers of lags; α , β , ψ and γ are parameters to be estimated; and μ represents the serially uncorrelated error terms. The test is based on the following hypotheses:

H_0 : $\gamma_i = \psi = 0$ for all i 's

H_1 : $\gamma_i \neq 0$ and $\psi \neq 0$ for at least some i 's.

At this point, it is necessary to examine the criteria for causality. The hypothesis was tested by using Chi (χ^2) statistics. If the values of the γ_i coefficient are statistically significant but those of the ψ are not, then X causes Y ($X \rightarrow Y$). On the contrary, if the values of the coefficients are statistically significant but those of the coefficient are not, then Y causes X ($Y \rightarrow X$). If both are significant, then there exists bidirectional causality between X and Y ($X \rightleftharpoons Y$). In a case of independence or no causal relationship between X and Y ($X \nleftrightarrow Y$).

3.4.4 Stability Test

The stability test is run to see whether the model used for forecasting is stable. For a set of n time series variables $y_{1t} = (y_{1t}, y_{2t}, \dots, y_{nt})'$ a VAR model of order p [VAR(p)] can be written as:

$$y_t = A_1 y_{t-1} + A_2 y_{t-2} + \dots + A_p y_{t-p} + \mu_t \dots \dots \dots (3.11)$$

Where the A_i 's are ($n \times n$) coefficient matrices and $\mu_t = (\mu_{1t}, \mu_{2t}, \dots, \mu_{nt})'$ is an unobservable zero mean error term. Under the above identity, the stability of a VAR can be examined by calculating the roots of:

$$(I_n - A_1 L - A_2 L^2 \dots) y_t = (L) \dots \dots \dots (3.12)$$

The characteristic polynomial is defined as:

$$(Z) = (I_n - A_1 z - A_2 z^2 \dots) \dots \dots \dots (3.13)$$

The roots of $|(Z)| = 0$ will give the necessary information about the stationarity or non-stationarity of the process. Characteristic roots having a location outside the unit circle is a required and sufficient requirement for stability. If so, then all variables and the complete rank are stationary.

3.4.5 The Impulse Response Function

Sims' (1980) introduced the idea of an impulse response function, which is frequently and almost exclusively linked to linear multivariate Markov models, such as VARs, and their decomposition. It is challenging to comprehend VAR models. Making an impulse response function (IRF) is one approach. The IRF tracks how

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF RESULTS

4.1 Data Presentation

Annual time series data were sourced from Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical bulletin and National Bureau of Statistics on Companies Income Tax (CIT), Value Added Tax (VAT), and Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) for the period of 35 years (1986-2021) which are presented in Appendix 1.

4.2 Descriptive Statistics of Data

The summary of descriptive statistics includes the mean, minimum and maximum values, standard deviation, skewness, kurtosis, and the Jarque-Bera test for the data, among other fundamental statistical characteristics of the data under examination. These descriptive statistics provide our data's behavior with a historical context.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	GDP	CIT	PPT	VAT
Mean	42703.33	997.9078	461.4125	483.8189
Median	34889	658.3	122.8	357.15
Maximum	94463.55	3201.32	1793.33	1398.08
Minimum	17180.55	4.81	1.1	7.7
Std. Dev.	23571.31	1046.759	576.6033	446.961
Skewness	0.728041	0.657074	1.032465	0.627382
Kurtosis	2.272674	2.051404	2.708341	2.155638
Jarque-Bera	3.973766	3.940224	6.523506	2.66861
Probability	0.137122	0.139441	0.038321	0.263341
Sum	1537320	35924.68	16610.85	13546.93
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.94E+10	38349665	11636499	5393901
Observations	36	36	36	28

Source: Computation using E-views 9, 2023

The Jarque-Bera test, which is a test of the normality distribution of the variables, appears to be crucial among the statistics presented in Table 1 among the other statistics. According to our findings and the Jarque-Bera statistics' P-values, all the variables were normally distributed because they had P-values greater than (0.05).

4.3 Correlation Matrix

A table displaying the correlation coefficients between the variables utilized in this study is called a correlation matrix. The correlation between the two variables is displayed in each cell of the table. This correlation matrix functions as a data summary, an input for more sophisticated analysis, and a diagnostic for sophisticated studies.

Table 2: Correlation Coefficients between the Variables

	GDP	CIT	PPT	VAT
GDP	1			
CIT	0.815468	1		
PPT	0.984604	0.757339	1	
VAT	0.992036	0.800245	0.989491	1

Source: Computation using E-views 9, 2023

According to Table 2, there is a significant and favourable correlation between the GDP, CIT, PPT, and VAT.

4.4 Unit Root Test

To prevent the issue of erroneous regression, we utilize the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test to check the stationarity of the variables. The unit root outcome is shown in the table below.

Table 3: Stationarity Test Result

Variables	Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Unit Root Test				Decision
	Critical Values	At level	Critical Value	At 1st Difference	
LGDP	-2.567984	-3.20032	4.458605***	-4.226815	I(1)
LCIT	-0.097227	-4.219126	6.024527***	-4.226815	I(1)
LVAT	-3.238054	-3.279051	-7.35812***	-7.246813	I(I)
LPPT	-2.337794	-4.219126	5.842179***	-4.234972	I(1)

Note: * 1% level of statistical significance; ** at 5%, statistical significance; * at 10% Statistical significance**

Source: Computation using E-views 9

All of the variables were not stationary at level, according to the results of the unit root tests performed using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) test, which is shown in Table 3. In other words, the LGDP, LCIT, LVAT, and LPPT were stationary at the first difference I(1), and were either significant at 1%, 5%, or 10%, depending on the situation. Thus, the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) was used to estimate the model.

4.5 Granger Causality Test

The co-integration test shows a long-term equilibrium relationship between the two variables, but additional testing is required to determine whether there is a causal relationship. The explanatory power of the regression can be significantly improved if variable A is useful in predicting B, i.e., the regression of B is based on previous values of B and past values of A are added. Then A can be referred to as B's Granger cause; otherwise, it can be referred to as B's non-Granger cause. The null hypothesis—that Granger causality exists—must be accepted because the p-value is less than the significant level of 5% ($P < 0.05$).

Table 4: Granger Causality Test Result

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.	
CIT does not Granger Cause GDP	34	0.51886	0.6006	
GDP does not Granger Cause CIT		3.22204	0.0545	Unidirectional
PPT does not Granger Cause GDP	34	9.5558	0.0006	
GDP does not Granger Cause PPT		4.37427	0.0219	Bidirectional
VAT does not Granger Cause GDP	26	3.04506	0.069	
GDP does not Granger Cause VAT		4.07342	0.032	Bidirectional
PPT does not Granger Cause CIT	34	1.32216	0.2822	
CIT does not Granger Cause PPT		7.18924	0.0029	Unidirectional
VAT does not Granger Cause CIT	26	3.95087	0.035	
CIT does not Granger Cause VAT		0.13861	0.8714	Unidirectional
VAT does not Granger Cause PPT	26	22.6801	6.00E-06	
PPT does not Granger Cause VAT		0.48172	0.6244	no causality

Source: Computation from E-views 9, 2023

From Table 4 above the findings on GDP, CIT; VAT and PPT are both granger causes of one another, meaning that there is a bidirectional relationship between the variables. While there is no Granger causality between PPT and VAT, there is unidirectional causality between GDP and CIT, CIT and PPT, and CIT and VAT.

4.6 Lag Length Selection Criteria

The number of lags to be included in the model before the Johansson co-integration test was determined using the optimum lag length selection criterion before the VECM technique was looked at. To avoid misspecification and autocorrelation issues, the best lag choice must be taken into account (Gonzalez, 2016). The outcome is displayed in Table 5 below:

Table 5: Optimal Lag Length Selection Criteria

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-759.6795	NA	4.01e+21	61.09436	61.28938	61.14845
1	-670.1202	143.2950	1.14e+19	55.20961	56.18471	55.48006
2	-639.9368	38.63467*	4.10e+18	54.07495*	55.83013*	54.56176

Source: Computation using E-views 9, 2023

*** indicates lag order selected by the criterion, LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level), FPE: Final prediction error, AIC: Akaike information criterion, SC: Schwarz information criterion and HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion**

Table 5 above shows that two maximum lags should be included in the model according to the Akaike information criterion (AIC), Hannan-Quinn information

criterion (HQ), and all other criteria except the Schwarz information criterion (SC).

As a result, the Akaike information criterion (AIC) will serve as our model.

4.7 Johansen Co-integration Test

The long-term relationships between integrated variables are made more understandable by co-integration analysis. It was employed in this study since Johansen's (1991) method provides the greatest likelihood for finite-order Vector Auto-regressions (VARs) and is simple to compute for such systems. The outcome is displayed below:

Table 6: Johansen cointegration Test

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.768531	70.10929	47.85613	0.0001
At most 1 *	0.651588	33.52651	29.79707	0.0178
At most 2	0.219698	7.167251	15.49471	0.5583
At most 3	0.037880	0.965390	3.841466	0.3258

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized		Max-Eigen	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.768531	36.58278	27.58434	0.0027
At most 1 *	0.651588	26.35926	21.13162	0.0084

At most 2	0.219698	6.201861	14.26460	0.5874
At most 3	0.037880	0.965390	3.841466	0.3258

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

The Johansen (1988) and Juselius (1990) approach is typically used to examine the co-integration connection between variables in the VAR model. The Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Companies Income Tax (CIT), Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT), and Value Added Tax (VAT) all passed the Johansen cointegration test. Table 6 above demonstrates that under the 5% level, test results in both the maximum eigenvalue test and the trace test are to accept the null hypothesis and at least one cointegrating equation exists. This indicates that the variables have enduring and stable equilibrium relationships. VEC modelling can proceed under the assumption that cointegration linkages exist.

4.8 Vector Error Correction Model (VECM)

It should be noted that the Error Correction Mechanism (ECM) aims to connect the co-integrating equations' short-run dynamics to their long-run static dispositions. The Vector Error Correction Method (VECM) was used to capture the short-run variation, and the outcome is shown in Appendix II.

4.9 VEC Residual Serial Correlation

Table 7: Serial Correlation LM Test

Lags	LM-Stat	Prob
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1	13.57461	0.6304
2	18.94134	0.2717

Probs from chi-square with 16 df.

Source: Computation using E-views 9, 2023

According to Table 7, the alternative hypothesis of serial dependency among error terms is the null hypothesis, which states that there is no serial connection in the error terms. It implied that this results analysis are trustworthy and free of serial correlation because the probability of the LM test in the result has values for the two-lag period of 0.6304 and 0.2717 which is greater than the 5% level of significance.

4.10 Impulse Response

Further analysis is performed using impulse response function and variance decomposition based on Vector Error Correction Model, and the results for 10 periods are acquired. This analysis is done to study the dynamic impacts of the model responding to certain shocks as well as how the effects are among the four variables. Individual coefficients from the Vector Error Correction Model for the vector-autoregressive model are difficult to interpret, as has been noted in the literature. It is challenging to comprehend VAR models. Making an impulse response function (IRF) is one approach. The IRF tracks how endogenous variables react to a shock of one standard deviation to one of the system's disturbance factors. The dynamic design of the VEC models allows for the transmission of this shock to all endogenous variables (Lutkepohl, 2001). As a result, the analysis of the model's dynamic features involves looking at the variance decompositions and impulse response functions.

The impulse response functions show the expected course over time of the variable to shocks in the innovations, tracing the dynamic reactions to the effect of shock in one variable affecting itself and on all other variables. Figure 1 plots these impulse response functions.

Figure 1: Plot of the Impulse Response Function

45

Source: Author's computation

The results for 10 Period are shown in Figure 1

Gross Domestic Product experiences a shock

Over time, the effect becomes apparent. Last but not least, a shock to PPT of one standard deviation has a positive but minor impact on GDP. PPT has little impact on GDP between periods 5 and 6.5. However, the impact returns as later periods demonstrate that PPT's shock responds favorably to GDP.

4.11 Variance Decomposition of GDP

Table 8: Variance Decomposition of GDP Result

Period	S.E.	LGDP	LCIT	LVAT	LPPT
1	0.160422	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.214064	95.30948	2.110210	2.569134	0.011172
3	0.359003	76.59182	12.66408	4.623789	6.120308
4	0.455133	79.67191	11.08167	5.429145	3.817274
5	1.110311	68.24019	7.347223	4.142537	20.27006
6	1.428246	79.03976	4.501934	3.925491	12.53281
7	5.478374	64.74615	3.568167	2.891410	28.79427
8	7.668482	78.58366	2.649787	2.630152	16.13640
9	32.37484	65.23620	2.535494	2.575864	29.65244
10	48.64399	79.53668	1.807503	2.382440	16.27337

Cholesky Ordering: LGDP LCIT LVAT LPP

Source: Computation using E-views 9, 2023

The results for 10 Period are shown in Table 8 and each period represents 3.5 years. For the first period, we can see that a shock to GDP during that period accounts for 100% of the variation in GDP (own shock), but no contribution was made by shocks to CIT, VAT, or PPT. CIT has a little greater short-term impact on GDP growth than PPT. However, over a longer period, VAT has a much greater impact on GDP growth than CIT and PPT. The change in GDP growth with the lengthening of the

period can be better explained by the shock to the VAT. In other words, beginning with period 3 and continuing through consecutive periods, VAT accounts for approximately 60% of the fluctuation in GDP.

CHAPTER FIVE

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Major Findings

With a particular emphasis on the Companies' Income Tax, Value Added Tax, and Petroleum Profit Tax, this research investigated the relationship between tax and economic growth in Nigeria. There is at least one co-integrating equation between the variables in the long run, according to the Johansen test of co-integration. The nature and degree of the association between tax and economic growth were determined by the study using a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM). A causal relationship between Real GDP and the various tax components was discovered using the Granger causality test. The following conclusions are supported by impulse response functions and variance decomposition analysis using Vector Error Correction Model (VECM):

- I. In the short run, a one standard deviation shock to CIT has a positive discernible effect on GDP; however, over the long run, it has a negative perceptible effect on GDP and reduces output.
- II. A one-standard-deviation shock to VAT has a significant and favourable impact on GDP in the short run. While in the Long-run the effect became noticeable.
- III. A shock to PPT of one standard deviation has a positive but minimal impact

on GDP. PPT has little impact on GDP between periods 5 and 6.5. However, the impact returns as later periods demonstrate that PPT's shock responds favourably to GDP.

As a result, the shock to the indirect tax (VAT) tends to have an increasingly large impact on GDP growth over time. The CIT and PPT, as well as the low level of tax compliance, can be ascribed to a variety of things, such as the complex and ineffective tax administration system, ambiguities in the tax rules, and a lack of transparency regarding the use of tax income for social services and obvious development.

5.2 Conclusion

The impact of the value-added tax (VAT) shock on GDP growth tends to expand dramatically over time. The CIT and PPT, as well as the low level of tax compliance, can be ascribed to a variety of things, such as the complex and ineffective tax administration system, ambiguities in the tax rules, and a lack of transparency regarding the use of tax income for social services and obvious development. For the tax system to be efficient and effective, it must produce officials who are well-paid, well-motivated, properly organized, and adequately equipped. Other major challenges facing tax authorities include the need to not only build but also utilize institutional and human capacity, funding, and logistics as well as finding solutions for tax evasion, fraud, and mismanagement of collected revenue, improving voluntary compliance, and speedy adjudication on legal matters. The system must

comply with straightforward, explicit, and simple tax regulations, and assessment and collection procedures must be easy to understand, open to the public, and client-friendly. Nigeria must create special tax tribunals and train specific tax judges.

5.3 Recommendations

Base on the above findings the study recommended as follows:

- i. To increase the level of Companies' Income Tax (CIT) and tax compliance in Nigeria, the government should make an effort to promote businesses by providing basic public services to every nook and cranny of the nation.
- ii. The government should stop all leakages in the petroleum industry so that the Petroleum Profit Tax (PPT) collected from Nigerian crude oil can support and advance Nigeria's economic growth. Additionally, the government should seek to reduce or completely eradicate the pervasive corruption in the administration of the petroleum profit tax.
- iii. To increase the government's Value Added Tax (VAT) base and provide a favourable environment for oil companies and innovation utilizing tax money.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

This study has contributed to knowledge in the following areas:

The insights gained from this study will benefit Nigeria's financial and tax authorities, raising the country's standard of living and stimulating economic growth

through accumulated revenues.

The study supports the Federal Inland Revenue Services, Federal Ministry of Finance, Budget, and National Planning of Nigeria, which are entrusted with formulating and implementing tax policy via the Federal Executive Council (FEC).

This study serves as a resource for academics, researchers, and scholars who want to conduct additional research in this area of study.

5.5 Limitations of the Study

This study would have been more effective if the data had been more easily accessible. This was notably true for collecting data on company income tax (CIT), value added tax (VAT) and petroleum products tax (PPT). Another limitation of the study was the time constraints and stressful nature of the research effort. Although, even with the time constraints, the best practice was acknowledged, and all the citations were referenced.

5.6 Suggestions for Future Studies

This study examines the impact of Tax on economic growth in Nigeria from 1986-2021. Therefore, I suggested for more research in the following areas:

- i. Investigate the appraisal of the Administration of Personal Income Taxation States in Nigeria
- ii. The effect of tax revenue on selected states in Nigeria
- iii. Examine the Problems of Government Tax Planning and Administration in Nigeria

- iv. Challenges of tax authorities, and taxpayers in the management of tax reform processes.

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APPENDIX I
DATA PRESENTATION

Year	GDP (#)	PPT (#)	CIT (#)	VAT(#)	LGDP	LPPT	LCIT	LVAT
1986	17180.55	4.81	1.1	0.00	0.097308	9.751533	1.570905	0.00
1987	17730.34	12.5	1.1	0.00	0.09758	9.783033	2.526049	0.00
1988	19030.69	6.81	1.55	0.00	0.438771	9.853808	1.919038	0.00
1989	19395.96	10.6	1.91	0.00	0.6493	9.87282	2.360684	0.00
1990	21680.2	26.91	2.99	0.00	1.096042	9.984155	3.292461	0.00
1991	21757.9	38.62	3.83	0.00	1.342316	9.987732	3.653664	0.00
1992	22765.55	51.48	5.42	0.00	1.689579	10.033	3.941129	0.00
1993	22302.24	59.21	9.55	0.00	2.25697	10.01244	4.08105	0.00
1994	21897.47	42.8	12.27	7.7	2.507548	9.994126	3.756601	2.04122
1995	21881.56	42.86	21.88	19.4	3.085495	9.9934	3.75789	2.965273
1996	22799.69	47.5	23.1	29.4	3.139833	10.0345	3.86073	3.380995
1997	23469.34	64.3	27.8	33.5	3.325036	10.06345	4.16356	3.511545
1998	24075.15	24.6	33.3	39.3	3.505557	10.08894	3.202746	3.671225
1999	24215.78	71.1	46.2	47.1	3.83298	10.09476	4.264087	3.852273
2000	25430.42	334.5	53.3	58	3.975936	10.1437	5.812637	4.060443
2001	26935.32	407.1	69.4	91.7	4.239887	10.20119	6.009059	4.518522
2002	31064.27	224.4	89.1	108.6	4.489759	10.34381	5.41343	4.687671
2003	33346.62	438	114.8	136.4	4.743191	10.41471	6.082219	4.915592
2004	36431.37	878.6	130.8	163.3	4.873669	10.50319	6.77833	5.095589
2005	38777.01	1352.2	170.2	192.7	5.136974	10.56558	7.209488	5.261135
2006	41126.68	1349.5	246.7	232.7	5.508173	10.62441	7.207489	5.44975

2007	43837.39	1132	332.4	312.6	5.806339	10.68824	7.031741	5.744924
2008	46802.76	2060.9	420.6	401.7	6.041682	10.7537	7.630898	5.995706
2009	50564.26	939.41	595.18	481.41	6.388868	10.831	6.845254	6.176714
2010	54612.26	1480.36	658.5	564.89	6.489968	10.90801	7.300043	6.336634
2011	57511.04	3070.59	654.45	659.15	6.483792	10.95973	8.029625	6.490957
2012	59943.79	3201.32	820.57	710.56	6.709994	11.00116	8.071318	6.566046
2013	63942.85	2666.37	963.45	802.68	6.870521	11.06574	7.888472	6.68796
2014	67977.46	2453.95	1173.49	802.96	7.067738	11.12693	7.805453	6.688311
2015	69780.69	1289.96	1268.98	767.33	7.145967	11.15311	7.162367	6.642922
2016	68652.43	1157.81	933.54	828.2	6.838981	11.13681	7.054284	6.719254
2017	69211.63	1520.48	1215.06	972.35	7.102546	11.14492	7.326782	6.879714
2018	79596.97	2467.58	1340.33	1108.04	7.200671	11.28473	7.810993	7.010348
2019	84064.36	2111.43	1607.32	1188.54	7.382324	11.33934	7.65512	7.080482
2020	93064.36	2316.45	1767.35	1388.64	7.882374	12.63934	7.85562	7.189482
2021	94463.55	2567.67	1793.33	1398.08	7.890685	13.25383	7.889671	7.247969

SOURCE: CBN Statistical Buletting and National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)

Where: GDP= Gross domestic product, PPT= Petroleum profit tax, CIT= Company income tax, VAT= Value added tax.

VAR Lag Order Selection Criteria

Endogenous variables: GDP CIT PPT VAT

Exogenous variables: C

Date: 06/30/23 Time: 15:11

Sample: 1986 2021

Included observations: 25

Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-759.6795	NA	4.01e+21	61.09436	61.28938	61.14845
1	-670.1202	143.2950	1.14e+19	55.20961	56.18471	55.48006
2	-639.9368	38.63467*	4.10e+18	54.07495	55.83013*	54.56176
3	-615.0999	23.84349	2.78e+18*	53.36799*	55.90325	54.07116*

* indicates lag order selected by the criterion

LR: sequential modified LR test statistic (each test at 5% level)

FPE: Final prediction error

AIC: Akaike information criterion

SC: Schwarz information criterion

HQ: Hannan-Quinn information criterion

Date: 04/07/23 Time: 12:52

Sample (adjusted): 1997 2021

Included observations: 25 after adjustments

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Series: GDP CIT PPT VAT

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 2

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.768531	70.10929	47.85613	0.0001
At most 1 *	0.651588	33.52651	29.79707	0.0178
At most 2	0.219698	7.167251	15.49471	0.5583
At most 3	0.037880	0.965390	3.841466	0.3258

Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized		Max-Eigen	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.768531	36.58278	27.58434	0.0027
At most 1 *	0.651588	26.35926	21.13162	0.0084
At most 2	0.219698	6.201861	14.26460	0.5874
At most 3	0.037880	0.965390	3.841466	0.3258

Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalized by b*S11*b=I):

GDP	CIT	PPT	VAT
-0.000134	0.003510	0.062356	-0.085567

0.000553	-0.004223	-0.028079	0.020149
0.000126	0.000932	-0.011485	0.010864
0.000161	0.001838	0.022051	-0.045802

Unrestricted Adjustment Coefficients (alpha):

D(GDP)	-333.1433	259.4226	-15.96357	-180.0292
D(CIT)	-205.3494	166.4143	-142.0615	35.27402
D(PPT)	-27.24488	-14.94171	24.39511	-4.961478
D(VAT)	3.599168	26.23446	0.254145	-1.572229

1 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood -631.8631

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

GDP	CIT	PPT	VAT
1.000000	-26.15716	-464.6679	637.6299
	(4.57058)	(66.7487)	(101.215)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(GDP)	0.044706
	(0.03454)
D(CIT)	0.027557
	(0.01470)
D(PPT)	0.003656
	(0.00217)
D(VAT)	-0.000483
	(0.00116)

2 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood -618.6835

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

GDP	CIT	PPT	VAT
1.000000	0.000000	119.9096	-211.5035
		(23.4551)	(33.2868)
0.000000	1.000000	22.34866	-32.46275
		(2.16288)	(3.06950)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(GDP)	0.188133	-2.264865
	(0.14137)	(1.36449)
D(CIT)	0.119562	-1.423537
	(0.05731)	(0.55316)
D(PPT)	-0.004605	-0.032538
	(0.00894)	(0.08626)
D(VAT)	0.014021	-0.098149
	(0.00307)	(0.02965)

3 Cointegrating Equation(s): Log likelihood -615.5826

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

GDP	CIT	PPT	VAT
1.000000	0.000000	0.000000	-40.15300
			(6.02470)
0.000000	1.000000	0.000000	-0.526578
			(1.08878)
0.000000	0.000000	1.000000	-1.428997
			(0.05033)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(GDP)	0.186123	-2.279743	-27.87437
	(0.14477)	(1.38381)	(17.2288)
D(CIT)	0.101671	-1.555930	-15.84587
	(0.05467)	(0.52255)	(6.50589)
D(PPT)	-0.001532	-0.009803	-1.559514
	(0.00839)	(0.08015)	(0.99792)
D(VAT)	0.014053	-0.097912	-0.515119
	(0.00315)	(0.03008)	(0.37446)

APPENDIX II

VECTOR ERROR CORRECTION MODEL

Vector Error Correction Estimates

Date: 04/07/23 Time: 14:20

Sample (adjusted): 1997 2021

Included observations: 25 after adjustments

Standard errors in () & t-statistics in []

Cointegrating Eq:	CointEq1			
LGDP(-1)	1.000000			
LCIT(-1)	-0.336483	(0.09317)	[-3.61150]	
LVAT(-1)	-0.896097	(0.23674)	[-3.78508]	
LPPT(-1)	0.870202	(0.50352)	[1.72823]	
C	-7.787251			
Error Correction:	D(LGDP)	D(LCIT)	D(LVAT)	D(LPPT)

CointEq1	-0.068535	-0.008022	-0.093146	0.720993
	(0.15295)	(0.60493)	(0.08954)	(0.16969)
	[-0.44810]	[-0.01326]	[-1.04024]	[4.24877]
D(LGDP(-1))	-0.147423	0.634756	0.140692	0.068451
	(0.26954)	(1.06608)	(0.15780)	(0.29905)
	[-0.54694]	[0.59541]	[0.89158]	[0.22889]
D(LGDP(-2))	-0.172994	0.544112	0.165949	-0.275384
	(0.26834)	(1.06131)	(0.15710)	(0.29772)
	[-0.64469]	[0.51268]	[1.05636]	[-0.92498]
D(LCIT(-1))	0.005437	-0.096857	0.023975	0.191648
	(0.07337)	(0.29019)	(0.04295)	(0.08140)
	[0.07411]	[-0.33378]	[0.55817]	[2.35432]
D(LCIT(-2))	0.059327	-0.462793	0.007993	0.226281
	(0.07063)	(0.27934)	(0.04135)	(0.07836)
	[0.84000]	[-1.65671]	[0.19330]	[2.88767]
D(LVAT(-1))	0.349614	1.402622	0.041759	0.934180
	(0.48129)	(1.90358)	(0.28177)	(0.53399)
	[0.72641]	[0.73683]	[0.14820]	[1.74944]
D(LVAT(-2))	0.049428	-0.836192	-0.144603	0.420192
	(0.24903)	(0.98496)	(0.14579)	(0.27630)
	[0.19848]	[-0.84896]	[-0.99183]	[1.52079]
D(LPPT(-1))	0.038130	-0.388422	0.020097	-0.681892

	(0.28744)	(1.13686)	(0.16828)	(0.31891)
	[0.13265]	[-0.34166]	[0.11943]	[-2.13819]
D(LPPT(-2))	0.955670	-1.256123	-0.646053	5.220818
	(1.01627)	(4.01952)	(0.59497)	(1.12755)
	[0.94037]	[-0.31251]	[-1.08586]	[4.63023]
C	0.117415	0.061563	0.144877	-0.348663
	(0.11026)	(0.43611)	(0.06455)	(0.12234)
	[1.06487]	[0.14117]	[2.24431]	[-2.85003]
R-squared	0.317580	0.244118	0.424456	0.729530
Adj. R-squared	-0.091872	-0.209411	0.079130	0.567248
Sum sq. resids	0.386026	6.038770	0.132309	0.475195
S.E. equation	0.160422	0.634496	0.093918	0.177988
F-statistic	0.775621	0.538264	1.229145	4.495452
Log likelihood	16.66062	-17.71502	30.04516	14.06286
Akaike AIC	-0.532850	2.217202	-1.603613	-0.325029
Schwarz SC	-0.045299	2.704752	-1.116063	0.162522
Mean dependent	0.190034	0.161158	0.154679	0.128773
S.D. dependent	0.153524	0.576955	0.097870	0.270565
Determinant resid covariance (dof adj.)		8.15E-07		
Determinant resid covariance		1.06E-07		
Log likelihood		58.89979		
Akaike information criterion		-1.191983		
Schwarz criterion		0.953238		
Varian ce Decom position				

of
LGDP:

Period	S.E.	LGDP	LCIT	LVAT	LPPT
1	0.160422	100.0000	0.000000	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.214064	95.30948	2.110210	2.569134	0.011172
3	0.359003	76.59182	12.66408	4.623789	6.120308
4	0.455133	79.67191	11.08167	5.429145	3.817274
5	1.110311	68.24019	7.347223	4.142537	20.27006
6	1.428246	79.03976	4.501934	3.925491	12.53281
7	5.478374	64.74615	3.568167	2.891410	28.79427
8	7.668482	78.58366	2.649787	2.630152	16.13640
9	32.37484	65.23620	2.535494	2.575864	29.65244
10	48.64399	79.53668	1.807503	2.382440	16.27337

Varian
ce
Decom
position
of LCIT:

Period	S.E.	LGDP	LCIT	LVAT	LPPT
1	0.634496	1.692057	98.30794	0.000000	0.000000
2	0.896937	3.690488	94.64091	1.453550	0.215052
3	0.973854	3.424633	91.76787	1.256357	3.551143
4	1.299264	25.70910	59.60710	1.547921	13.13588
5	2.696434	60.93877	15.53667	1.873559	21.65100
6	6.640901	72.99550	2.577159	2.218321	22.20902
7	17.46163	74.87338	0.534402	2.425643	22.16657
8	44.11280	75.94319	0.314829	2.476766	21.26522
9	114.0439	75.55088	0.410654	2.498375	21.54009
10	286.0865	76.04864	0.394849	2.503908	21.05260

Varian
ce
Decom
position
of
LVAT:

Period	S.E.	LGDP	LCIT	LVAT	LPPT
1	0.093918	5.136002	12.89441	81.96959	0.000000
2	0.153155	5.228233	26.20769	68.38877	0.175306
3	0.214486	11.02085	25.99710	46.90457	16.07748
4	0.366896	46.57190	14.88903	18.03283	20.50624
5	1.217456	68.52725	1.413414	2.195367	27.86397
6	2.738498	77.84929	0.296352	1.560798	20.29355
7	8.461411	72.87165	0.660282	2.093765	24.37430
8	18.76740	78.20408	0.194318	2.258454	19.34315
9	54.84637	73.40032	0.744629	2.439541	23.41551
10	123.0113	77.88389	0.263661	2.454743	19.39771

Varian
ce
Decom
position
of
LPPT:

Period	S.E.	LGDP	LCIT	LVAT	LPPT
1	0.177988	59.00021	3.286613	2.782541	34.93064
2	0.332991	76.81167	0.999199	3.287332	18.90180
3	1.384075	66.87442	2.510850	2.948679	27.66605
4	2.555384	79.27150	0.736983	2.804655	17.18686
5	8.906899	69.74344	1.543819	2.636189	26.07655
6	16.99449	79.68752	0.424413	2.529651	17.35842
7	56.18427	70.85372	1.242487	2.544154	25.35964
8	111.3414	79.43915	0.319313	2.478388	17.76315

9	354.8156	71.60305	1.088599	2.525064	24.78329
10	727.3028	79.07439	0.277783	2.476087	18.17174

Cholesky
Ordering:
LGDP
LCIT
LVAT
LPPT
